

Improved Simplified Glowworm Swarm Optimization Algorithm

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Abstract- Aimed at the poor optimizing ability and the low accuracy of the glowworm swarm optimization algorithm (GSO), a simplified glowworm swarm optimization algorithm (SGSO) was put forward in this paper, which omitted the phases of seeking dynamic decision domain and movement probability calculation, and meanwhile simplified the location updating process. Moreover, elitism was introduced to improve the capacity of searching optimal solution. It was applied to the unimodal and multimodal benchmark function optimization problems. The improved SGSO algorithm is compared with the basic GSO and other swarm intelligent optimization algorithms to demonstrate the performance. Experimental results showed that SGSO improves not only the precision but also the efficiency in function optimization.

Keywords- glowworm swarm optimization; swarm intelligence; function optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

META-HEURISTIC algorithms provide a new perspective for solving complex problems by mimicking the biological behaviors and nature phenomenon, with the characteristics of high robustness, low complexities, excellent efficiency and superb performance, compensate the lack of searching and calculation for finite solutions and high complexity in traditional algorithms.

As a significant branch of meta-heuristic research, swarm intelligence algorithms, which inspired by the behavior of birds, fish, ants, and bee colonies and so on, is applied to search global optimum of many problems. Besides the characteristics of the meta-heuristic algorithms, swarm intelligent algorithms have the advantages of easy operation and good parallel architecture. In recent years, novel swarm intelligent algorithms for optimization have sprung up continually and have driven a high tide of researches on swarm intelligence. For example, particle swarm optimization algorithm (PSO), proposed by Kennedy J, Eberhard R.C. [1] in 1995, imitated the behavior of birds; bacterial foraging optimization algorithm (BFO) [2], introduced in 2002, simulated the foraging of bacteria; artificial bee colony algorithm (ABC) [3], introduced in 2005, mimicked the behavior of bee colonies for searching honey. Swarm intelligence optimization algorithms are widely applied in many scientific field including function optimization and

combination optimization [4- 6], NP-hard problems [7, 8], data mining [9- 11], engineering and process [12, 13], biotechnology [14] and other fields.

Glowworm swarm optimization algorithm (GSO) is a nature inspired heuristic intelligent algorithm, proposed by Krishnan and K.N. and Ghose D. in 2005 [15], which simulated behavior of glowworm group in moving by using luciferin to attract other glowworms around or foraging. The greater value of luciferin, the brighter of the glowworm, the more attractive will be.

Glowworm swarm optimization algorithm has been applied to many fields, such as multimodal function and combination optimization [16, 17], robotics applications [18-20], and wireless sensor networks [21, 22]. Also, it is widely used in some NP-Hard problems like TSP [23] and 0-1 knapsack issues [24]. Glowworm swarm optimization algorithm has some shortcomings, such as low accuracy in later iterations, slow convergence speed and easy to be trapped into local optimal solutions.

A simplified glowworm swarm optimization algorithm (SGSO) is proposed to improve the performance of the original GSO algorithm. Comparison shows good performance in the field of function optimization problems with the basic GSO, which embodies the ability of fast convergence speed and strong searching ability in contrast to PSO, BFO, ABC [25] and the fruit fly optimization algorithm (FOA) [26, 27] which is a novel swarm intelligent algorithm proposed by Pan in 2011, mimicking the foraging behavior of fruit flies for searching global optimum.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the basic concepts and principles of glowworm swarm intelligent optimization algorithm. Section III provides the simplified glowworm swarm optimization algorithm and corresponding principles, location update, elitism, boundary control, procedure of SGSO and computation complexity. Results from experiments are described in Section IV, where we test two groups of experiments for SGSO. One is the comparison between the basic GSO and SGSO in different dimensions, and the other is the comparison among other